

THE USE OF PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES IN THE CLASSROOM AND THE RESULTS OF THE LESSON

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Annontatsion: In the process of teaching foreign language courses, advanced pedagogical technologies are required to use interactive, innovative methods and communication methods. Foreign language teaching in the Republic of Uzbekistan is based on the recommendations of the European Commonwealth of Independent States (CEFR) to assess the knowledge and skills of foreign language teachers new methods and requirements are being developed.

Key words: used, important, achieve, working, education

In addition, the teaching of the students in the process of teaching, the use of various pedagogical technologies and modern techniques will help them to develop independent thinking, communicative skills, emotional communication among students, approach to science, research, effective use of scientific literature, and, most importantly, to study, to science, and to the profession that he chooses. To achieve this result, in practice, it requires integrate innovative and information technologies.

Nowadays, interest and attention to the application of innovative technologies in the educational process is intensifying, and one of the reasons for this that, in the current educational system, modern technology will help them to search for their knowledge, to independently analyze, and even make conclusions. In this process, the teacher creates conditions for personal development, formation education and upbringing, and at the same time, fulfills the functions of management, guidance. In the course of the course the student becomes the main figure. Knowledge,

experience, and interactive methods of pedagogical technology and pedagogical skills provide students with skillful, advanced skills.

The introduction of modern communication technologies in the educational process is one of the most important issue, namely targeted and accurate use of them, increasing the interest of students in the foreign language through them. This creates opportunities for the use of innovative technologies in education and the demand increases.

Teaching methods involve a variety of working methods and forms that can be used to achieve the objectives of a specific pedagogical process. Numerous teaching methods have been created on the basis of the various forms and that are used and practiced in practice, and this process continues. The way that the way, the way a particular act of learning is shaped, is a form of self - study that serves to achieve that goal.

Here are some of the paths that can be used for the activity that is required to be performed as a means of action, and the path chosen according to the intended purpose. For example, education can be taught through: family education, schooling, preschool education, teacher training, books, computers, exhibition aids, announce Similar tracks can also be used to teach a similar number, arithmetic meanings. By using these methods, different techniques are used to perform the action. For example, after selecting any of the foregoing methods to teach the doctrine, each of these methods is used for the purpose that is considered appropriate. These are the methods used by a teacher, a teacher in a family, a preschool education institution, and the school education; computer, books and other educational tools. Each path chosen by the same number to teach arithmetical acts implies using specific techniques. Each action is carried out in a specific way and in the appropriate method.

Thus, the use of interactive methods in teaching subjects is unique. Careful learning and practical application of each interactive method used in education can extend student thinking and have a positive impact on the problem's solving.

Increase creativity and activity of students. When analyzing different theoretical and practical problems through interactive methods, the students' knowledge, skills, qualifications are expanded and extended.

The aforementioned will require a proper analysis of interactive teaching methods and the need to classify them on that basis. Below you will find general comments on this issue. Classification of the techniques can be divided into interactive learning strategies, interactive graphic organizers. Studying foreign languages open the door to great opportunities. Today's linguist can not only live in harmony with time, but also learn from the latest news, enjoy the true knowledge of the world literature and literature, communicate with peers and colleagues abroad, share ideas and experiences possible. Therefore, studying foreign languages is equally important for students and teachers. One of the most effective ways to learn English, especially in English, is the game method. Your game may be used in English language. For example, in the "Find out" exercise, the instructor and the reader will share. The pupil must find words that are not relevant to the teaching tools. At the end of the game, the student who correctly performs the assignment will say the words.

Teaching English science through the use of different games is invaluable. Playing various games during the classroom increases the passion for learning science in the classroom, and encourages passive learners to participate better in the classroom, creating a competitive environment for students in the classroom and at the same time creating a cosmic atmosphere. It also increases students' respect for their teachers. Below you will be provided with games that help you increase the efficiency of teaching during English lessons.

"Last man standing" game

This game is a fast game. But it gives some time to think. This game encourages learning together, that is, when other students say, the rest of the students are thinking about themselves. You will need a little to play. And all students should be in a circle. You need to choose a theme. For example, things found in a kitchen,

food, profession and so on. The game begins by throwing a ball to student. The reader speaks an English word on the subject and throws the ball to the next reader. Anyone who accepts the ball must make a statement on that subject. If they repeat the words or if they can not find a word within a few seconds, they will quit the game and watch the game seated. Do not worry, they're still learning. You can change this game in a slightly different way. Instead of speeches on a subject, every student can say something different to the next reader. For example, you can start the game by saying "say something red" (biror qizil narsani ayting). The first reader who holds the Copter can then "strawberry" and then drop a topic and throw it to the other. This makes the game somewhat challenging, since the reader should know what the subject should look like before thinking about a word.

"Pictionary" game

Many English speakers Pictionary are familiar with the drawing game. For illustration purposes, you can use simple whiteboard or white magnetic card. Divide the class into 2 groups and draw the table on the side of the board for each team. You write scores here. A team of the team will be released. And then chooses one of the many reversible words and draws that word on a board. And others will have to find. The score will be awarded to the team that won 10 points is the winner.

"Charades" game

The Charades game is similar to the Pictionary game, but the main difference is that there are no drawings to describe the word. This game is a great help for your pupils when you are slow, bored, and sleepy. Wake them up and move them! Write down words in several rectangular sheets for students to choose from. It's easier than bruising. But you are a little more complicated, but you can use all the words that the students know.

Make a class of two teams. Each student chooses a paper - reader and expresses it in action. He team will have to find the same word in three minutes. A score is given for each correct answer. The team that scored 10 points is the winner.

"Taboo words" game

Taboo worlds help students to apply synonyms and vocabulary recipes. The class is divided into two and the teams sit in the opposite one of their teams.

The tutor goes behind the pupils and keeps the world a on a large sheet of paper. Students sitting on the floor should not be able to see the world. The team member sitting on the seat will have 3 minutes to tell the word that you hold. Most importantly, they should not use the word at all. Advice to play in older classrooms. If there are more than 12 students in your class, there may be some noise and chaos in this game. In this case, you will only have 5 or 6 subgroups, and only attend the turn.

“20 Objects” (20 Items) game

Check that your pupils have the memory and the value of the world at the same time. You will only need items on board and 20 rooms classrooms. You can even use your purse or your stuff. Put all of the item on the table and tell your readers to look at them. Then close all the items in one minute with paper (something similar). Ask all your readers to return to their place of residence and write their articles in English. After finishing all things, write the playlist on the dashboard and ask the students to check themselves. Alternatively, you may want to read the words one by one and determine if they find it.

Reference:

1. “You will only” **2021**
2. “One minute with” **2007**